

On closer examination, $\hat{Q}$ is seen to register a rise with increase in initial concentration of the chloride solutions, followed by a fall at still higher contributions (Table 1). The long-range ion-solvent interactions in the bulk solution are expected to make positive contributions to $\hat{Q}$ in dilute solutions. These contributions decrease at higher concentrations owing to a partial overlapping of the hydration zones (i.e., mutual screening effect of ions⁹). The latter causes a narrowing down of the aforesaid difference of ordering in water structure between the bulk and the given soil, leading to a less negative $\hat{Q}$ at higher concentrations.

However, at still higher concentrations (e.g., above 0.10–0.15 M; Table 1), ion-pairing may become important; the latter may lead to an enhancement of $\hat{Q}$ due to a net fall in the extent of long-range ordering in water. It is indeed interesting to note in this connection that a minimum in the activity coefficient of aqueous $MgCl_2$ solutions occurs within the concentration range 0.4–0.5 M as well.

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Apparent Molar Volumes of L-Proline and L-Hydroxyproline in Methanol-Water Mixtures

J. S. SANDHU* and GURBIR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002

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AMINO acids have been quite useful as models¹ for understanding the thermodynamic behaviour of peptides and proteins in solution. Volumetric properties and heat capacities of amino acids in

different aquo-organic media have been investigated¹⁻⁴. But similar investigations at different temperatures are rather scarce although such a study is likely to give an insight into the mode of solute-solvent interactions. As an extension of our studies^{5,6} of apparent molar volumes of amino acids in water and methanol-water mixtures, we report herein the apparent molar volumes of L-proline and L-hydroxyproline in methanol-water mixtures.

Experimental

L-Proline and L-hydroxyproline were (LOBA and E. Merck, G. R.) were used as such and dried before use under reduced pressure for 40 h and stored over anhydrous calcium chloride in vacuum desiccator. Methanol (AnalaR) was purified by the recommended method⁷. All the solutions were prepared by weight on molar basis in double-distilled degassed water and vacuum corrected. The procedure for density measurements have been described previously⁸. The density data were accurate within $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The densities measured at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K have been used to calculate the apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of the solute using equation (1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_o - d)}{c d_o} + \frac{M}{d_o} \quad (1)$$

in which the terms have their usual significance. The plots of ϕ_v against concentration are linear and have positive slopes in case of both the amino acids in the temperature range studied. Limiting apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 are obtained using least-square fit to the plot of the experimental values of ϕ_v against molar concentration, c , using equation (2),

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v c \quad (2)$$

where, $\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}^0$, is the infinite dilution partial molar volume and S_v the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^0 , S_v and standard errors, σ_v , obtained in 10, 20 and 30% (w/w) of methanol-water mixtures are listed in Table 1. The values of ϕ_v^0 in aqueous medium are also included in Table 1 along with the literature values. As seen from Table 1, the present ϕ_v^0 value of L-proline at 298.15 K agrees very well with the literature value⁹, but is slightly lower than the reported values⁹⁻¹¹. For L-hydroxyproline, there exists only one value for ϕ_v^0 at 298.15 K as reported by Ogawa *et al.*¹⁰ which is larger than the present value. The values of ϕ_v^0 at temperatures other than 298.15 K could not be compared due to lack of literature data. It is apparent from Table 1 that ϕ_v^0 increases with temperature in aqueous and methanol-water mixtures in the temperature range 298.15–318.15 K. It appears that primary and secondary solvation layers are formed around the zwitter ions. Since the solvent molecules from the

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES AT INFINITE DILUTION (ϕ_v^0) WITH THEIR STANDARD ERRORS (σ_v), SLOPES (S_v) AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF TRANSFER AT INFINITE DILUTION ($\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$) FOR L-PROLINE AND L-HYDROXYPROLINE IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Amino acid	Methanol % (w/w)	ϕ_v^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			S_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³)		
		298.15 K	308.15 K	318.15 K	298.15 K	308.15 K	318.15 K
L-Proline	0	81.59 ± 0.04 ^σ	82.71 ± 0.04	83.52 ± 0.04	5.63	4.89	4.59
		81.7 ^a					
		81.0 ^b					
		82.87 ^c					
	10	82.65 ± 0.08 ^d					
	20	79.70 ± 0.15 (-1.89)	80.98 ± 0.13 (-1.73)	81.87 ± 0.14 (-1.65)	2.40	2.73	3.49
	30	78.20 ± 0.11 (-3.39)	80.20 ± 0.10 (-2.79)	81.34 ± 0.12 (-2.18)	4.63	4.34	3.52
L-Hydroxyproline	0	80.43 ± 0.16 (-1.16)	81.57 ± 0.13 (-1.14)	82.61 ± 0.09 (-0.91)	3.16	4.99	5.06
		83.73 ± 0.11	84.29 ± 0.07	84.91 ± 0.09	3.17	2.81	2.19
		84.45 ^c					
	10	81.83 ± 0.13 (-1.90)	82.78 ± 0.13 (-1.51)	83.95 ± 0.10 (-0.96)	3.87	4.53	3.21
	20	80.89 ± 0.14 (-3.34)	81.45 ± 0.11 (-2.84)	82.40 ± 0.11 (-2.51)	5.81	6.25	6.25
	30	82.56 ± 0.14 (-1.17)	83.16 ± 0.17 (-1.13)	84.00 ± 0.17 (-0.91)	6.22	7.12	7.29

σ = Standard errors. * $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ values are given in parentheses. ^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRef. 10. ^dRef. 11.

secondary solvation layers are released at higher temperatures resulting in the expansion of the solution more rapidly than the pure solvent, they must account for an increase in the observed ϕ_v^0 values^{1,2}.

The volumetric behaviour of solutes in solution can provide information concerning solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions. The infinite dilution partial molar volumes are, by definition, independent of solute-solute interactions and thus can be used to examine solute-solvent interactions. The volumes of transfer are calculated using equation (3),

$$\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0 = \phi_v^0(M.S) - \phi_v^0(W) \quad (3)$$

where, $\phi_v^0(M.S)$ is apparent molar volume at infinite dilution in mixed solvent and $\phi_v^0(W)$ the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution in pure water. The calculated $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ values (Table 1) at three temperatures are plotted for the two amino acids against percentage of methanol (Fig. 1).

It is evident from Table 1 that the ϕ_v^0 values of the two amino acids at all the three temperatures decrease with the addition of methanol which results in negative $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ (Fig. 1) with increase in temperature; the magnitude of $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ value becomes less indicating that solute-solvent interactions are weaker at higher temperatures. However, the negative values of $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ become more negative with the addition of methanol till minima are attained, then increase as the alcohol concentration is raised. This effect has also been observed by Mishra and Ahluwalia³ who reported that the apparent molal volumes of transfer of glycine, α -alanine, β -alanine, α -amino-n-butyric acid and L-valine decrease at low t-butanol concentrations and then increase. Kaneshina *et al.*^{1,2} also observed the same trend for the partial molar volumes of sodium alkyl sulphates in methanol-water mixtures. The decrease in ϕ_v^0 and the negative $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ of both the amino acids upto 20% (w/w) methanol, which is the region of maximum structure enhancement^{4,15}, may be due

Fig. 1. Plots of $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ (L-proline and L-hydroxyproline) vs percentage of methanol at different temperatures: (●) 298.15, (▲) 308.15 and (○) 318.15 K.

to the increase in electrostriction in the presence of methanol. Thus the electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in the volume of solvent caused by the zwitterionic portion of the amino acid, is increased in mixed solvents as compared with that in pure water. Since electrostriction primarily reflects amino acid-solvent interactions,

It can be inferred that the minima in $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^\ddagger$ values correspond to the region where solute-solvent interactions are maximum.

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Oxidation Products of Taraxasteryl Acetate and Molecular Rearrangement of its Epoxide

U. K. SOM, A. K. SIL, K. E. HAQUE and C. P. DUTTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

and

K. P. DHARA

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

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A number of interesting molecular rearrangements as a result of epoxide ring opening has been reported in recent years¹. In continuation of our investigation^{2,3} on the molecular rearrangement involving epoxide ring opening in pentacyclic triterpenoid skeleton taraxa-20 α ,30 α -oxido-3 β -yl acetate (2) was prepared by the action of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid⁴ on taraxasteryl acetate (1). During epoxidation two other products were also isolated which are believed to be formed through the intermediacy of 2. The α -orientation of epoxy function in 2, m.p. 274-75°, [α]_D+102° (CHCl₃), was justifiable from both ¹H nmr studies and stereochemical viewpoint, C₃₀-C₃₀ bond now being favourably β -oriented.

The structure of the major rearranged product obtained during the aforesaid reaction was proposed as 3. The compound 3, C₃₂H₅₂O₄ (M⁺ 500), m.p. 232° [α]_D+2.07 (EtOH) was shown to possess an enclaved E-ring bearing keto carbonyl and hydroxyl functionalities (1 715 and 3 400 cm⁻¹, respectively). The acetate carbonyl appeared at 1 720 cm⁻¹ as one of the twin peaks. In the ¹H nmr spectrum a signal at δ 3.45 (1H, m) was assigned to methine proton at C₃₀-bearing OH group. A two-proton broad signal was discernible at δ 3.70 which turned into a one-proton singlet on deuteration. This signal was attributed to C₃₀-proton and C₃₀-hydroxylic proton, the latter would disappear after the treatment with deuterium oxide. The other methylenes, methylene and methine protons resonated at their usual regions. The mass fragmentation pattern (Chart 1) of the compound was in conformity with the structure proposed and as rationalised for taraxastane class of triterpenoids⁵.

The minor component 4, C₃₂H₅₀O₃ (M⁺ 482) m.p. 215°, [α]_D+3.7° (EtOH), showed λ_{max} 220 nm (ϵ 6000) accounting for the presence of an α,β -unsaturated keto group in the molecule. Occurrence of an infrared absorption peak at 1 695 cm⁻¹ along with the one at 1 720 cm⁻¹ (acetate carbonyl) also suggested the above conjecture. From mechanistic consideration and appearance of a one-proton multiplet at δ 6.66 it led to the structure 4 which essentially originated from 3 by the loss of one molecule of H₂O. The assignment of structure 4 was